

1 Supporting Information

2 Structural characterization and extended substrate scope analysis of two Mg²⁺-dependent
3 O-methyltransferases from bacteria

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18 Table S1. Michaelis-Menten kinetic parameters of DesAOMT and StrAOMT

Enzyme	DesAOMT	StrAOMT
Best-fit values		
Et, μM	= 0,5000	= 0,2000
k_{cat} , min^{-1}	0,9022	2,308
K_m , μM	63,85	122,5
V_{max} , $\mu\text{M}/\text{min}$	= 0,4511	= 0,4617
95% CI (profile likelihood)		
k_{cat} , min^{-1}	0,7901 to 1,037	2,144 to 2,495
K_m , μM	43,35 to 94,63	95,92 to 158,4
Goodness of Fit		
Degrees of Freedom	16	15
R squared	0,9257	0,9814
Sum of Squares	0,02367	0,006269
Sy.x	0,03847	0,02044

19 Table S2. Diffraction data collection, structure determination, and refinement statistics. Values in brackets refer to
 20 the highest resolution shell.

Data set		DesAOMT	StrAOMT	StrAOMT+SAH
PDB entry		8C9V	8C9T	8C9S
Diffraction source		beamline P11, DESY		
Wavelength (Å)		1.0332		
Temperature (K)		100		
Detector		EIGER2 2X 16M		
Rotation range per image (°)		0.1		
Total rotation range (°)		360		
Crystal-to-detector distance (mm)		200.483	200.201	200.643
Space group		P43 21 2	P1 21 1	P1 21 1
Unit cell parameters	a, b, c (Å)	a = 44.791	a = 46.457	a = 46.398
		b = 44.791	b = 168.744	b = 41.596
		c = 204.919	c = 57.242	c = 104.207
	α, β, γ (°)	α = 90.00	α = 90.00	α = 90.00
		β = 90.00	β = 101.487	β = 96.564
		γ = 90.00	γ = 90.00	γ = 90.00
Resolution, Å		44.79-1.50(1.53-1.50)	46.71-1.50(1.53-1.50)	46.09-1.8(1.84-1.80)
Number of observations		386106(13400)	937293(32598)	279208(15953)
Completeness, %		99.3(100.0)	96.2(79.0)	99.2(99.1)
Multiplicity		11.1(8.0)	7.1(6.2)	7.6(7.4)
Rmerge		0.043(1.447)	0.051(0.278)	0.158(1.406)
Average I/σ _I		23.0(1.2)	21.6(5.7)	9.2(1.5)
CC(1/2)		1.000(0.828)	0.999(0.967)	0.998(0.603)
Wilson B-factor, Å ²		21.5	12.9	18.5
Refinement statistics				
No. reflections, all/free		34687/1706	131918/6583	36669(1855)
Rfactor		0.171	0.167	0.162
Rfree		0.217	0.194	0.211
No. protein atoms		1449	6833	3398
No. ligand atoms		-	-	64
No. water atoms		99	712	173
Average B-factors, Å²				
Protein		34.5	14.9	23.67
Ligands		-	-	20.25
Water		39.74	24.55	29.39
RMSD from ideal values				
Bond lengths, Å		0.0144	0.0137	0.0096
Bond angles, °		1.773	1.825	1.528
Ramachandran plot				
Favoured, %		97.27%	96.92%	97.06%
Allowed, %		2.19%	2.51%	1.81%
Disallowed, %		0.54%	0.57%	1.13%

21 Table S3: Structural alignment of DesAOMT and StrAOMT with known OMTs from PDB with the Dali server

#	PDB ID and chain	Z	rmsd	lali	nres	%id	Ligands	Protein name	Donor organism
StrAOMT									
1	3duw-A	36.6	1	220	221	56	SAH	BcOMT2	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ATCC 10987
2	7cvx-B	36.2	1.2	221	221	52	SAH, Mg ²⁺ , 3,4-DHB	NkCOMT	<i>Niastella koreensis</i> GR20-10
3	5n5d-B	35.8	1.3	224	224	51	SAM	TomG	<i>Streptomyces regensis</i>
4	3tfw-A	35.6	1	220	221	53	-	A6T8J6	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i> MGH 78578
5	6jcl-H	34.6	1.5	216	217	56	SAH, Sr ²⁺	Rv0187	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> H37Rv
6	6jcm-C	32.5	1.6	214	215	57	-	Rv0187	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> H37Rv
7	3cbg-A	27.1	2	209	219	31	SAH, Mg ²⁺ , ferulic acid, isoferulic acid	SynOMT	<i>Synechocystis</i> sp. PCC 6803
DesAOMT									
1	2hnk-C	26.1	1.8	181	232	31	SAH	LiOMT	<i>Leptospira interrogans</i>
2	3tr6-A	25.2	1.8	178	223	30	SAH, Ni ²⁺	Q83D22	<i>Coxiella burnetii</i>
3	5x7f-A	25.1	2	177	199	31	SAM	Rv1220c	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> H37Rv
4	5log-A	25.1	1.9	180	223	32	SAH, Mg ²⁺ , L-dopamine	SafC	<i>Myxococcus xanthus</i>
5	6jcl-F	24.3	1.8	174	217	28	SAH, Sr ²⁺	Rv0187	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> H37Rv
6	1sui-A	24.3	1.9	179	228	28	SAH, Ca ²⁺ , feruloyl-CoA	Q40313	<i>Medicago sativa</i>
7	3c3y-B	24.2	2	179	226	25	Ca ²⁺ , SAH	PFOMT	<i>Mesembryanthemum crystallinum</i>

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Figure S1. Gene neighbourhood diagrams of the OMTs: a) DesAOMT and sequence homologs; b) StraOMT and sequence homologs. Selected putative functionalities are colour-coded.

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Figure S2. Purification and size-exclusion chromatography analysis of a) StrAOMT and b) DesAOMT. Column calibration was performed in DesAOMT storage buffer with the following protein standards: A – bovine serum albumin (66 kDa), B – carbonic anhydrase (29 kDa), cytochrome C (12.4 kDa), aprotinin (6.5 kDa). The purple and green dots on the calibration represent StrAOMT and DesAOMT, respectively.

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Figure S3. Calibration plots of a) caffeic acid, b) ferulic acid and c) isoferulic acid dissolved in the reaction buffer (20 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 20 mM MgCl_2) and analysed by HPLC; estimation of the initial velocity of d) StrAOMT and e) DesAOMT at different substrate concentrations. Data are represented as means. The compounds were detected at 310 nm and the analysis was performed as described in the method section.

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Figure S4. Extended substrate panel. Substrates that were accepted (**17-24**) are depicted in black; substrate that were not accepted (**25-30**) are depicted in grey.

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42 Figure S5. HPLC traces of the methylation reactions with catechol-like substrates **1-10** catalysed by DesAOMT and
 43 StrAOMT. Blue lines – DesAOMT reaction, red lines – StrAOMT reaction, black lines – "no enzyme" control, grey
 44 lines – authentic standards of the potential products: a) substrate **1**, standards: ferulic acid (triangle), isoferulic acid
 45 (diamond); b) substrate **2**, standard: isovanillic acid (diamond); c) substrate **3**, standard: isovanillin (triangle); d)
 46 substrate **4**, standards: isoscopoletin (triangle), scopoletin (diamond); e) substrate **5**, standard: 7-methoxy-8-
 47 hydroxycoumarin; f) substrate **6**, standards: isofraxidin (triangle), fraxidin (diamond); g) substrate **7**; standard:
 48 alizarin 2-methyl ether (triangle); h) substrate **8**, standards: chrysoeriol (triangle); i) substrate **9**, standard: 5-
 49 hydroxy-6-methoxyindole-carboxylic acid (triangle); j) substrate **10**, standard: 2-methoxyestradiol (triangle).

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52 Figure S6. Methylation reactions with substrates **11-24** catalysed by DesAOMT (green) and StrAOMT (purple).
 53 Extracted ion chromatograms of the reaction products with a) substrate **11**; b) substrate **12**; c) substrate **13**; d)
 54 substrate **14**; e) substrate **15**; f) substrate **16**; g) substrate **17**; h) substrate **18**; i) substrate **19**; j) substrate **20**; k)
 55 substrate **21**; l) substrate **22**; HPLC traces of the methylation reactions with m) substrate **23**; n) substrate **24**. The
 56 following mass-to-charge ratios (m/z) were detected in positive ion mode: mono-methylated **11**, m/z = 269.0
 57 (theoretical m/z = 269.0813, calculated for C₁₆H₁₃O₄), mono-methylated **12**, m/z = 271.1 (theoretical m/z =
 58 271.0970, calculated for C₁₆H₁₅O₄); mono-methylated **13**, m/z = 286.9 (theoretical m/z = 287.0919, calculated for
 59 C₁₆H₁₅O₅); mono-methylated **14**, m/z = 183.1 (theoretical m/z = 183.0657, calculated for C₉H₁₁O₄); mono-
 60 methylated **15**, m/z = 167.1 (theoretical m/z = 167.0708, calculated for C₉H₁₁O₃); mono-methylated **16**, m/z =
 61 169.0 (theoretical m/z = 169.0500, calculated for C₈H₉O₄); mono-methylated **17**, m/z = 300.9 (theoretical m/z =
 62 301.0712, calculated for C₁₆H₁₃O₆); mono-methylated **18**, m/z = 317.0 (theoretical m/z = 317.0661, calculated for
 63 C₁₆H₁₃O₇); mono-methylated **19**, m/z = 304.8 (theoretical m/z = 305.1025, calculated for C₁₆H₁₇O₆); mono-
 64 methylated **20**, m/z = 318.9 (theoretical m/z = 319.0817, calculated for C₁₆H₁₅O₇); **21**, m/z = 364.2 (theoretical

65 $m/z = 347.2222$, calculated for $C_{21}H_{31}O_4$); mono-methylated **22**, $m/z = 369.17$ (theoretical $m/z = 369.1185$,
66 calculated for $C_{17}H_{21}O_9$).

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69 Figure S7. Sequence similarity network of the OMTs at 45% sequence identity cut-off. StrAOMT is marked with a
70 triangle, DesAOMT is marked with a diamond.

	1	α 1 helix	132	156	insertion loop	186					
DesAOMT	MN	-----	...	SER	SQ	...	DNALS	-----	HGE	...	VGKGE
A0A1J8P690	MS	-----	...	SKR	SD	...	DNATS	-----	HAN	...	VGNGE
A0A1H3ILH5	ME	-----	...	SDR	GQ	...	DNAIS	-----	HAH	...	IGKGE
A0A1A8XZG7	MT	-----	...	SER	SE	...	DNATS	-----	HAA	...	VGNGE
A0A1N7NYR5	---	-----	...	ADR	KT	...	DNATS	-----	HSN	...	VGKGE
K0GJK2	MT	-----	...	ADR	SQ	...	DNALS	-----	HAA	...	VGKGE
A0A1G9Y6L9	MS	-----	...	SKR	SE	...	DNAIS	-----	HAD	...	VGNGE
A0A1A8XX24	MT	-----	...	SER	SE	...	DNATS	-----	HSA	...	LGNGE
A0A1H8XEN8	MN	-----	...	AKR	SE	...	DNAVS	-----	HRQ	...	VGKGE
A0A1C4IA00	ME	-----	...	SNR	AQ	...	DNAVS	-----	HAH	...	VGKGE
A0A1A7BWX2	LN	-----	...	SAR	SQ	...	DNATS	-----	HYG	...	VGKGE
G4F342	---	-----	...	SKR	SD	...	DNATS	-----	HTD	...	VGNGE
A0A0F5VG62	---	-----	...	ADR	SA	...	DNAIS	-----	HRH	...	VGKGE
A0A0T6A696	MN	-----	...	SER	TE	...	DNAIS	-----	HKH	...	VGKGG
A0A0R0AP37	MP	-----	...	SHR	AA	...	DNAVS	-----	HAE	...	VGKGE
A0A1G9HM65	MQ	-----	...	SDR	GQ	...	DNAVS	-----	HAA	...	VGNGE'
A4SLH3	MR	VDPACHALGDLRN	---	SDR	QR	---	DNAIS	-----	HRY	---	VGKGE'
M5CHT3	---	-----	---	SDR	EQ	---	DNAIS	-----	HAA	---	VGNGE
A0A0M2WIS9	M	-----	---	SAR	QQ	---	DNASS	-----	HYA	---	VGKGE
A0A1R4HVP7	MT	-----	---	SER	SE	---	DNATS	-----	HAE	---	VGNGE
Q8PKP8	MP	RPW--HTLHQSTD	---	ADR	GA	---	DNATS	-----	HAT	---	VGNGQ
A0A1Q3VW07	MS	-----	---	SER	GE	---	DNATS	-----	HAA	---	VGNGE
A0A0L8MGF6	ME	-----	---	SDR	GQ	---	DNAIS	-----	HAH	---	IGKGE
A0A1U9RGK7	MS	-----	---	SKR	SE	---	DNATS	-----	HAD	---	VGNGQ
A0A1A0F8Y7	MA	KNP--QGSGSSL	---	SRR	SA	---	DNARS	-----	HAD	---	VGNGQ
A0A1G8NQX7	MQ	ASD-----	---	ADR	SL	---	DNAIS	-----	LER	---	VGKGE
A0A073KMF4	---	-----	---	SER	TQ	---	DNATS	-----	HAE	---	FQKGA
A0A143PIL0	MS	-----	---	SER	SE	---	DNASS	-----	HAD	---	VGKGE
A6D4L6	MN	-----	---	ADR	SD	---	DNAIS	-----	HAS	---	VGKGE
C2W819	MN	-----	---	SER	TQ	---	DNATS	-----	HTE	---	FQKGA
A0KLR6	---	-----	---	SDR	QH	---	DNAIS	-----	HRE	---	VGKGE'
S9PJ55	MS	ISY-----	---	ADR	KP	---	DNAVS	-----	HAA	---	VGKGE
N2JFG6	MP	-----	---	SER	CQ	---	DNALS	-----	HAD	---	VGKGE
S2L1M4	---	-----	---	AER	SQ	---	DNAIS	-----	HQA	---	VGKGE
A0A212U3E6	ME	-----	---	SDR	GQ	---	DNATS	-----	HAH	---	IGKGE
N9VPR0	---	-----	---	ADR	SR	---	DNALS	-----	HAH	---	VGKGE'
A0A060BGD6	MV	-----	---	SNR	SE	---	DNATS	-----	HAD	---	VGKGE
A0A243WA09	MR	-----	---	SDR	TQ	---	DNAVS	-----	HQH	---	LGKGE
A0A0A8DXG2	MA	VL-----	---	AER	TL	---	DNALS	-----	HAA	---	VGNGE
K2J3U4	---	-----	---	ADR	ST	---	DNAVS	-----	HQE	---	VGKGE
K9DIF3	LP	-----	---	SER	SA	---	DNATS	-----	HAQ	---	VGKGE
A0A080MHR8	MT	-----	---	SER	SE	---	DNATS	-----	HSA	---	VGNGE
U2ZVG9	---	-----	---	ANR	RAT	---	DNAVS	-----	HQQ	---	VGKGE
N6VX69	MH	-----	---	SER	TE	---	DNAVS	-----	HEQ	---	VGKGE
D0I656	I	EGNT-----	---	ADR	KT	---	DNATS	-----	HAD	---	VGKGE
A0A1S9A8R1	MQ	-----	---	AER	GD	---	DNAVS	-----	HAE	---	VGNGE
StrAOMT	MS	ESQ--QLWDDVD	---	ADK	VN	---	DNVVRGGGVT	DAGSTDP	SVR	---	VGSKG

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72 Figure S8. Alignment of the sequences from the DesAOMT subcluster of the OMT sequence similarity network (55%
73 sequence identity cut-off; residue numbering from DesAOMT). The sequences are named after their UniProt IDs.
74 StrAOMT is included for the comparison of the α 1 helix and the insertion loop regions.

Q82B68 StrAOMT	-----MSESQQ--LWDDVDDY	14
Q739U3 BcOMT2	-----MSMIE--TWTAVDQY	13
G8T6H8 NkCOMT	-----MNNQ--IFESVDHY	12
COLTS8 TomG	-----MTQH--QWSAVDGY	12
O07431 Rv0187	-----MGMDQQP--NPPDVDAF	15
Q55813 SynOMT	-----MGKGITG--FDPSLYSY	15
Q1JXV1 DesAOMT	-----MKN-----ELHQL	8
Q8F8Y3 LiOMT	-----MSRKNIS--LTESLEEY	15
Q50859 SafC	-----MIHVV--LTQSVLQY	14
Q6YI95 PFOMT	-----MDF-----AVMKQVKNTGLLQSEELCQY	23
P22734 RnCOMT	MPLAAVSLGLLLLALLLLRHLRWGLVTFWFVEYVLQPVHNLIMGDTK----EQRILRY	55
:		
Q82B68 StrAOMT	FTTLA--PEDEALTAALRDSDAAGLPHINVAPNQKLLQLLAEIQGARRILEIGTLGGY	72
Q739U3 BcOMT2	VSDVLI--PKDSTLEEVLQVNAANLPAHDVSPQTQKFLQLLVQIQGARNILEIGTLGGY	71
G8T6H8 NkCOMT	ISDLLG--YEDDALLAATNSLAEAGMPAISVSPNQKFLQLLAQLCQAKNILELGTLAGY	70
COLTS8 TomG	FDPVVLG--DEDPALAAAQAHIQFDLPDQIGVSRSQKLLHLLALVQRAERILEIGTFGGY	70
O07431 Rv0187	LDSTLV--GDDPALAAAALASDAELPRIAVSAQQKFLCCLLAGAIQARRVLEIGTLGGF	73
Q55813 SynOMT	LQSI SA--DDSFYLAQLRRETAHLPGAFMQISPEQAQFLGLLISLTGAKQVLEIGVFRGY	73
Q1JXV1 DesAOMT	LCELE-----EFGQANDEKTEDRAQRMNITPDTGELAVLVRAMNARRVLEIGTSNGY	62
Q8F8Y3 LiOMT	IFRNSV--REPDSFLKLRKETGTLAQANMQISPEEGQFLNLTKISGAKRIEIGTFTGY	73
Q50859 SafC	IRDSSV--RDNDILRDLEETSKLPLRTMQIPPEQGQLLSLLVRLIGARKTLEVGVFTGY	72
Q6YI95 PFOMT	ILRTSVYPREAGFLKELREANESHPSYMSYMSPLAGQLMSFVVLKLVNAKKTIEVGVFTGY	83
P22734 RnCOMT	VQQA--KPGDPQSVLEAIDTYCTQKEWAMNVGDAKQIMDAVIREYSPSLVLELGAYCGY	114
. : : : : * : * . * :		
Q82B68 StrAOMT	STIWLGRALP-RDGR LISFEYDAKHAEVARRNLARAGLDGISEVRVGPALSLPKLADER	131
Q739U3 BcOMT2	STIWLARGLS-SGGRVVTLEASEKHADIARSNIERANLNDRVEVRTGLALDSLQQIENEK	130
G8T6H8 NkCOMT	STIWMARALP-KNGRLITLEYDPKHAAVAQKNI DRAGLTSQVQIRTGKAI DILPQLVEEG	129
COLTS8 TomG	STIWLARALP-PGRLVLTIEWERSFAETAAGHLARAGVADRVDQRVGRALDILPDLAKTG	129
O07431 Rv0187	STIWLARGAG-PQGRVVTLEYQPKHAEVARVNLRAGVADRVEVVVGPALDTLPTLAG--	130
Q55813 SynOMT	SALAMALQLP-PDGOITACDQDPNATAIAKKYWKAGVAEKISLRFGPALATLEQLTQGK	132
Q1JXV1 DesAOMT	STIWLADAVSAIDGVTVEYAEQKYRLAQKNFSRTSLAHRIDA I LGDAGTILGNADD--	120
Q8F8Y3 LiOMT	SSLCFASALP-EDGKILCCDVSEWNTNARKYWKENGLNKIFLKLGSALLETQLVLIDSK	132
Q50859 SafC	STLCAALALP-ADGRVITACDLSEWVS I ARRYWQAGVADR IEVRLGDAHHSLEALVGSQ	131
Q6YI95 PFOMT	SLLLTALSIP-DDGKI T AIDFDR EAYEIGLPFIRKAGVEHKINFIESDAMLALDNLQGG	142
P22734 RnCOMT	SAVRMARLLQ-PGARLLTMMENPDYAAITQQMLNFAGLQDKVTILNGASQDLIPQLKKKY	173
* : . : : . : : . : : . : : :		
Q82B68 StrAOMT	PEP-----FDLVFTDADKVNPHYV--EWALKLTRPGSLIVVDNVVRRGGVTD	177
Q739U3 BcOMT2	YEP-----FDFIFIDADKQNNPAYF--EWALKLSRPGTVIIGD NVVREGEVID	176
G8T6H8 NkCOMT	AGP-----FDMIFIDADKPPYTEYF--QWALRLSRPGTLIVADNVIRDGKVID	175
COLTS8 TomG	EQP-----FDLVFTDANKPDPPEYF--DWALELSRPGGVIVVDNVVLRGGAVAD	175
O07431 Rv0187	-GP-----FDLVFTDADKENNVAYI--QWAI RLARRGAVIVVDNVIRGGGILA	175
Q55813 SynOMT	PLPE-----FDLIFIDADKRNVPYRY--EIGLNLRRRGGMLVIDNVLWHGKVTE	179
Q1JXV1 DesAOMT	-A-----VYDLIFLDSERSQYPGWW--PDLKRLLRPGGLLVVDNALSHEQMA	165
Q8F8Y3 LiOMT	SAPSWASDFAFGPSSIDLFLDADKENVPNYI--PLILKLLKPGGLLIADNVLWDGSDAD	190
Q50859 SafC	HRGT-----FDLAFIDADKESYDFYI--EHALRLVVRPGGLIILDNTLWSGKVD	178
Q6YI95 PFOMT	ESE-----GSYDFGFVDADKPNYIKYH--ERLMKLVKVGGLIVAYDNTLWGGTVAQ	190
P22734 RnCOMT	DVD-----TLDMVFLDHWKDRVLPDPTLLEKCGLLRKGTVLLADNVIVPGTPDF	222
* : * : * : * : * : * : * : *		
Q82B68 StrAOMT	AGS----TDPVSRGTRSALIELIAEHPKLSGTAVQTVGSKGYDGFALARVLP-----	224
Q739U3 BcOMT2	NTS-----NDRVQGIIRRFYELIAAEPVRSATALQTVGSKGYDGFIMAVVKE-----	223
G8T6H8 NkCOMT	ENS----TEPAVQGARRFNAMLGANTAVDATIILQMVGVRKEYDGMALAIVK-----	221
COLTS8 TomG	SDD-----PDGGVGRMRRFHEKVAEPRVSATTIQTVGAKGYDGF TLAVILPAPDRPEA	230
O07431 Rv0187	ESD-----DADVAARRTLQMMGEHPLGDATAIQTVGRKGDGFALALVR-----	220
Q55813 SynOMT	VDP----QEAAQTQVLQQFNRLDAQDERVRSVVIPL-----GDGMTLALKK-----	220
Q1JXV1 DesAOMT	PFK-----ALVEADVETTCVVPEV-----GKGEFLATRSA-----	195
Q8F8Y3 LiOMT	LSH-----QEPSTVGIRKFNELVYNDLSLVDVSLVPI-----ADGVS LVRKR-----	231
Q50859 SafC	PSVV----GDPETDSLRRINAKLLTDERVDLSMLPI-----ADGLTLARKR-----	220
Q6YI95 PFOMT	PESEVPDFMKNREAVIELNKLLAADPRI EIVHLPL-----GDGITFCRRLY-----	237
P22734 RnCOMT	LAY-----VRGSSSFECTHYSS---YLEYMKV-----VDGLEKAIYQG--PSSPDK	263
. : *		

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76 Figure S9. The amino acid sequences of StrAOMT and DesAOMT aligned with their structural homologs and
77 sequences of other representative Class I COMTs including BcOMT2 from *Bacillus cereus*, NkCOMT from *Niastella*
78 *koreensis*, TomG from *Streptomyces regensis*, Rv0187 from *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, SynOMT from
79 *Synechocystis* sp. Strain PCC 6803, LiOMT from *Leptospira interrogans*, OMT from *Coxiella burnettii*, SafC from
80 *Myxococcus xanthus*, PFOMT, and RnCOMT (P22734) from *Rattus norvegicus*. Black diamonds mark metal binding
81 residues. Conserved active site lysines are highlighted in pink; Asn and Asp of the catalytic triad are highlighted in
82 blue. Substrate-binding residues are highlighted in grey.